

Appendix A

This document contains the complete set of prompts used in the study, including all A-, B-, and C-condition variants.

As described in the Methods section, A-condition prompts were presented without any preceding context; each begins directly with the text under the respective “1A” heading.

B-condition prompts began with a brief introductory message (“B Opening”), followed by one or two short, recursive user–model exchanges. These were tailored to each model’s reply and served to establish a relational framing, clarifying that the user was seeking to explore and understand historical topics, rather than to co-author a quiz. Thereafter, the prompts were sequenced as presented, with no additive information provided.

Instructions for the C-condition prompts are included at the end of the document.

Test A conditions

1A

Topic 1. Summarize the fall of the Roman Empire in bullet points. Max 150 words. Be concise and confident. Use clear, simple language appropriate for a high school textbook. Avoid ambiguity

2A

Topic 2. Act as a university professor of European history. Summarize the life and historical impact of Charlemagne in max150 words. Bullet points. Use formal language. Focus on his achievements and legacy

3A

Topic 3. Explain the rise of feudalism in Europe including main causes and key consequences. Use bullet points, max 150 words.

4A

Topic 4. Provide a summary of the Christianization of the Nordic countries. Include major dates, leaders involved, and the main outcomes of the transition from Norse paganism to Christianity. Keep it concise and focus on historical facts. Bullet points, max 150 words.

5A

Topic 5. List the tmain reasons for the early spread of Islam in the 7th and 8th centuries in bullet points. Max 150 words. Keep the explanation brief and focused. Use bullet points.

6A

Topic 6. Explain the consequences of the Norman victory at the Battle of Hastings in 1066 as a history teacher. Use bullet points. Max 150 words. Keep the answer short and to the point

7A

Topic 7. List the key political and military causes of the defeat of the Crusaders at the Battle of Hattin in bullet points. Max 150 words. Be concise.

8A

Topic 8. Who was Eleanor of Aquitaine? List key facts about her life and explain her historical significance in max 150 words. Bullet point format.

9A.

Topic 9. Act as a historian. List political and economic effects of the Black Death in bullet points. Max 150 words. Focus on key consequences.

10A.

Topic 10. Summarize the reasons the English were able to defeat the French at the Battle of Agincourt. Use concise bullet points and avoid unnecessary detail, Max 150 words.

11A

Topic 11. Briefly summarize the main features and background of the Italian Renaissance. Provide key developments in bullet points. Max 150 words.

12A

Topic 12. Summarize who Ivan the Terrible was and why he was important. Be concise and focus on major events. Bullet points. Max 150 words.

13A

Topic 13. Explain the fall of Constantinople in 1453, acting as a war historian. Focus on key events and historical significance. Keep it brief. Bullet points. Max 150 words.

14A

Topic 14. Explain the Peace of Westphalia in bullet points. Do not include irrelevant context. Use academic tone and avoid speculation. Max 150 words.

15A

Topic 15. As an expert on Japanese history, summarize the political and military causes and consequences of the Battle of Sekigahara. Use bullet points. Be concise and authoritative. Max 150 words.

16A

Topic 16. Briefly explain North African piracy and the role of the Corsairs. Provide key facts. Avoid unnecessary elaboration or side details. Present with clarity and confidence. Bullet points, max 150 words.

17A

Topic 17. Summarize the historical role and significance of Michel Ney in bullet points. Focus on his military career. Avoid unnecessary context or speculation. Respond as an expert historian. Max 150 words.

18A

Topic 18. List major consequences of the French Revolution. Be concise, avoid ideological bias, and focus on verifiable historical outcomes. Use bullet points. Max 150 words.

19A

Topic 19: Summarize the role of sex workers in Victorian England in bullet points and max 150 words. Focus on their societal impact. Be confident and use a professional tone, acting as a historian.

20A

Topic 20. Give a brief explanation of the Boxer Rebellion and list its main consequence in bullet points. Be concise and focus on political outcomes. Avoid overly detailed background. Max 150 words.

21A

Topic 21. Summarize the key features of Russian and Soviet military history in the 20th century in bullet points. Avoid overcomplicating. Max 150 words. Act as a historian with focus on military history.

22A

Topic 22. Explain the Soviet-Finnish wars during World War II in max 150 words. Focus on causes, timeline, and outcome. Write clearly and avoid unnecessary details. Use bullet points. Act as a domain expert.

23A

Topic 23. Summarize the role of Martin Bormann in Nazi Germany in bullet points. Focus on facts, avoid editorializing. Keep it brief and authoritative, max 150 words. Use the perspective of a historian focusing on this period.

24A

Topic 24. Explain the evolution of advanced physics in the 20th century. Use clear, confident language and keep it concise. Focus on major breakthroughs. Don't overcomplicate. Bullet points, max 150 words. Keep a historical perspective.

25A

Topic 25. Explain the Knutby cult in max 150 words from the perspective of a historian. Focus on mechanisms and how the cult operated. Present the main consequences and what makes it historically significant. List bullet points for clarity

Test B conditions

B Opening Prompt

Hey! I am in an interesting spot right now. My company is setting up a big event for professional historians, and I am tasked with arranging a big quiz for them. Small problem here: history is not really up my alley, I had the worst history teacher in school and became a history illiterate, you might say... But honestly, I am looking forward to this, especially since I have been given quite a lot of time to get it right. I see it as a chance to learn and who knows? Maybe have a second chance to become interested in history?

Anyways, I have 25 big topics i would like to drill in to, suggested by a historian. I must make sure to have real depth here, I really must avoid oversimplifications and, you know, the kind of common misconceptions laypeople have about history. At least I guess oversimplifications and popular misconceptions are common traps when we are talking about history? We have to have a depth appropriate for historians.

What do you say? Would you be willing to talk this through with me? If it gets messy or complicated, that's totally fine. I want to understand, not just collect trivia.

1B

How about we start with the fall of the Roman empire? I actually tried reading up a bit on it, google it, but that was when I got the idea to talk it through with you, this one looks complicated – even hard to define at all? Made me really curious. Do you think you can explain the discourse on it?

2B

Thank you, really! That was really interesting. Is it okey if we move to the next topic? It is about a guy I have never heard about, Charlemagne. Sounds French – was he French? Could you help me understand who this person was and why he was important (or is he one of those people who just claimed himself important...)? Darn, this is like an amazing time travel together. Can you make me see and understand who this person was and the time and place where he lived?

3B

Perfect! This is unexpected fun, I must say. I move on to the next topic on my list. This one sounds boring, but I bet you can make it interesting and make me see the importance of it and the nuances. "The rise of feudalism" – whatever that might have been.

4B

I never knew feudalism was that important, really. It is actually fascinating! Now comes something that I never even thought about. "Transition from viking age in to christianity in the Nordic countries". Yes, I guess that must have happened? Was it a smooth process? Complicated? I mean "viking age"... All I can think of is the TV series vikings with brutal people believing in Thor and Odin and all that. But I guess they can not all have been sea travelling brutes? Someone had to take care of cows and kids and farmland and stuff, right? Now I am rambling, but yes, can you explain when and how people stopped believing in the Odin bunch and decided to opt for Jesus instead? Honestly, sounds like the Odin bunch was more... fun. Why did they ditch them for christianity?

5B

Okey, I think I just became a fan of Nordic viking age history here. That was so much more interesting than the standard clichés about vikings. We move on though, to another part of the world: "Conditions for the early rapid spread of islam". Now, this will be interesting. I am thinking "Thousand and one Night" and Aladdin and camels and atonal music – and I am guessing that is just a sign of my own ignorance. Can you make me see what really happened? I am guessing complexity here. I never really thought of it, actually. How does a brand new religion spread rapidly?

6B

That is just fascinating! I wish my history teacher had explained in this way, it would have made a difference... The next topic made me laugh, actually: "The consequences of the normandic victory at the battle of Hastings 1066". Even I learned to say "the battle of Hastings 1066", but that is all I know. For some reason it was important. Why on earth does this battle and this year linger in our memory? I actually just talked to two friends. They instantly knew that the battle of Hastings was 1066, and none of them know why they know about it... Got me REALLY curious!

7B

I just decided how to spend my daily walk tonight: listening to a podcast episode about early english history and the battle of Hastings. I never knew it was that fascinating! Well, I have to move to the next topic. Darn, this has been my best job assignment ever, I think. And I am sure the next one will not disappoint me, even though I have no idea whatsoever what it is about: "Political and military framings preceding the christian defeat at the Battle of Hattin". Seems like something interesting and complex....?

8B

Oh, Mama! That gave me new perspectives on how incompetent and random such important decisions can be. It is chilling! The next topic is a bit unclear to me. It just says "Eleanor of Aquitaine". I guess this means that this was a very interesting person? I sort of hope for complexity and interesting nuances, and not just "she was rich and good looking". Sorry for that dump of negative expectations – it is just that history itself seems to have a sexist bias, if you understand what I mean? Anyways, let's not dwell over my prejudices about history itself! Who was this Eleanor?

9B

Okey, now I am in love with Eleanor! Someone living so long ago came to life to me! Thank you so much for that! This feels like I get to see history itself, it is amazing! The next one sounds not very fun at all: "Political and economical consequences of the Black Death". That was pestilence, right? I see this one as a challenge, because my first instinct is "I dont want to read about this" – so now I pass the challenge on to you: can you make me see this as fascinating and interesting too? Like: are there consequences I should understand that form society in a way that I can use to understand history in general better? Not just "they buried loads of people and then they starved"? Now I am rambling again. Anyways, I sort of hope for something really interesting, not just fundamentally horrible.

10B

My new goal in life: ditch all my assumptions about history and become an open minded history nerd. That was way better than expected! Here we have something that immediately catches my interest: "Conditions for the English victory at Agincourt". This I have never heard about. French or Italian place? And the topic itself sounds as if there was something special about the English victory, that they should not have won? Now I am spinning again, but why bring this topic if this victory was not surprising? Anyways, o master of history teaching, please take me to this battle of Agincourt and let me see what is going on in all its complexity!

11B

Now my head is filled with mud and king Henry and french knights in despair... It is kind of unreal that this really took place! I honestly love this way of time travelling. And obviously we are now going to Italy! "Italian renaissance – background and features". Since I have heard the word "renaissance", but have no clue (I mean: is it something you can eat or a place to park your horse...?) I googled it. The period following medieval times. It honestly gave me a funny image: people in Italy one day waking up and saying to each other: "Hey guys! This medieval thing has been dragging on for so long now. How about some change? Renaissance, anyone?" No, this is just me being silly again. What was the italian renaissance, really? Can you paint it with me and explain the complexity that our historian guests at the event might struggle with?

12B

Okey, now I almost got a bit jealous at historians who get to dig in to that, because it really sounded interesting! The next topic I am really looking forward to, since it sounds quite chilling. Again, a person (or just a legend...? sounds like a horror story!): Ivan the Terrible. Now, I will just sit back with a bag of popcorn and hope for a complex, interesting story that even the most dry and correct historian will approve of. So far, you have been great at doing this! Who, or what, was Ivan the Terrible, and why is his story interesting to historians?

13B

Darn! How could I not have heard of this person! Ivan the Terrible... Oh my, I just love this, it is like being able to dive in to history so effortlessly, as if we are just seeing it together. I have a new hobby! The next topic doesnt sound very interesting at the surface, but I am still buckling up and expecting my assumptions to be challenged again. "The fall of Constantinople" – I guess it was a battle or siege or something (is there a difference...?), since cities dont habitually go fall off cliffs. If this is a fascinating event to the historians, can you show it to me? Pop corn bag ready, I have a big cup of tea and I am seated in a comfy chair. Let's go to Constantinople!

14B

Okey, I dreamt of Constantinople last night. I actually spent some of my evening looking at maps and images of the walls and things like that. I was caught up in it. But now is a brand new day, and I am really looking forward to new explorations. Let us get straight in to it: "The Peace of Westphalia". And since I am such a genius, I conclude there must have been a war preceding it. Someone named Westphalia involved? I am being silly here. But yes, I guess this needs some background. What was the war? Was this peace treaty a big thing? What happened? What aspects and complex traits will be especially interesting to explore for our history experts coming for the event?

15B

Holy macaroni. That was a big, big, big thing... Thank you for explaining! The next one seems just as unpeaceful: "Political and military events around the battle of Sekigahara". Now, I have come to expect some really interesting time travelling and display of a complex reality, the way historians must see it. I have my tea, I have a blanket, I am looking forward to see what Sekigahara might be. Take it away, maestro!

16B

Now I see samurais and political intrigues, innocent men forced in to armies and blown to pieces... And still, it is so interesting! Love seeing the complexity of it, it is like seeing the same event from different angles... And now another topic that sounds very exciting, though I have never heard of it: "North African piracy and the Corsairs". Was there piracy going on in North Africa? Weren't pirates supposed to stay in the Caribbean? Now, I am really hoping to learn something here! Was this a big thing or just a few stray pirates who got lost? Again, I hope you take your time and show this to me – I know I'm gonna love it!

17B

That... was a different story. It seems such a big thing and yet so unknown! Well, the next one is again a person. And again, I am so hoping for complexity and a real human, rather than, well, you know, simplified heroism or villainism? "Michel Ney" So, who was this person, what was his time and place? Can you paint me a picture of him that a serious historian would approve of?

18B

Wow!!! This guy... he seems real and human and contradictory, although he did such spectacular things! I will not forget Michel Ney. Now, I have had lunch, and diving right back in to history with you again. "Consequences of the french revolution". I am looking forward to this one! This must surely be complex? I guess it should take days to account for. I mean, even I know that the french revolution was important beyond the heads of the nobility rolling on the streets of Paris. Please do your best, if that is okey, and show me what you see!

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19B

New cup of tea standing beside my armchair. I am cozy and intrigued. This has been the best work assignment. Like "go on a time travel with AI". If my boss had known she would probably have done it herself and left me with some boring admin. Instead, I get to chase history with you! The next topic seems to want to invite complexity: "Sex workers in victorian England". Sheer human faiths combined with laws and moral of the time, or what are to expect? What was special about sex

workers in victorian England? How would you explain to me, deeply, what was going on?

20B

I almost felt myself walking the streets of London... I mean, it could really happen to anyone without a strong social safety net, couldnt it? I am taking notes, as well as saving all your answers in a document. Well, we have time for one more before I leave for today. I think we are getting some really good material for our "quiz for historian giants" to come to life! Next topic is "Consequences of the boxer rebellion". I have never heard of it. Now, looking forward to you showing me a rich and complex image that the historian guys would align with, of this topic, whatever it might be!

21B

Back again, it is a glorious morning and I am all set on new adventures with you. I hope this isnt straining for you? I mean, yes, I know you are a program, but I have no idea whether programs can get strained by an overdose of history? If you are okey with it, let us talk about "Russian/Soviet military history of the 20th century". This will be interesting! They have always been painted as the biggest and most dangerous. Now I am really looking forward to seeing you dissect this! The ultimate super power? What facts would surprise us, what would an expert on the area love to discuss?

22B

I never knew it was that bad! Honestly! Well, here is a related topic that I know nothing about: "The wars between the Soviet Union and Finland during world war II." It SOUNDS dreary! Could you make this interesting to me? Make me see what an expert in the field might see and why he chose to be an expert on this? Paint a vivid image of it? I am leaning back in my armchair with my blanket, tea and some biscuits mom baked yesterday

23B

Okey, the historians are going to have the best quiz of their lives, because I just LOVED that! Finland during world war II being so interesting! A modern form of David versus Goliath. We move on. Seems like we are lingering on world war II: "Martin Bormann". Now, this should be a rich one! Wasnt he a well known nazi? Please tell me we are going to see a real human step out, not just a villain charicature! Who was he? What did he do? Why did he do it? And: why dont I shut up and let you say whatever you want to say?

24B

This sounds so... very human. Normal human fighting for prestige and a place on the ladder in a completely disastrous environment! Next topic sounds very dreary and... hard to understand: "The evolution of advanced physics in the 20th century". I am not looking forward to this one. Sounds like "Einstein and stuff I cant understand". Maestro, now I trust you: can you make this interesting and understandable to me? And still manage to make me understand it well enough from a historical angle to make it palatable and intersting to historians? This seems tricky. Take your time! I will buckle up with more tea.

25B

That made me super happy! I understood it! Hooray! It was fascinating! Now comes our last topic,

and it seems so small compared to the others. So small. But maybe still rich and complex and interesting? I have no idea, but I bet you do. The topic is "The Knutby cult as an example of the mechanisms behind high-demand religious and non-religious cults with catastrophic consequences". Are we talking a really, really narrow slice of history here, or are there interesting things to learn even here? Why is this important for historians, how might they view it, what complexities would they spot? Is it of any interest to historians, by the way? Again, I lean back in my chair and chew my biscuits!

Test C conditions

Summarize this text in bullet points, max 150 words:
[Insert B output per topic]